

Challenges to the implementation of the European approach to countering disinformation

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Since 2016, the issues involving fake news, disinformation online and post-truth have become topics of considerable public interest and have, therefore, become the subject of numerous media publications, as well as of a significant amount of scholarly research. The countries around the world have begun to actively seek solutions in order to be able counteract this phenomenon and its effects in the 21st century.

The events that are often referred to as having been a catalyst for such processes involve the US presidential election won by Donald Trump and the Brexit campaign in Britain to leave the EU. They showed the potential of disinformation to change public opinion and even influence the results of national elections and referendums.

The topic continued to be relevant during the COVID-19 pandemic. In February 2020, the Director-General of the World Health Organization, Tedros Ghebreyesus, emphasized the need for a reliable information environment dominated by facts, rationality and solidarity, not by fear, rumors and stigmas. He argued his thesis by pointing out that *“we are not just fighting an epidemic, we are fighting an infodemic”*¹.

The information war that has accompanied the war in Ukraine has turned disinformation into a major weapon. In October 2022, the European External Action Service (EEAS) stated that since the start of the war, there had been a noticeable spike in disinformation narratives promoted by the Russian information ecosystem. The EEAS reports that the EU has detected over 1200 cases of disinformation², targeting both Ukraine and the EU and individual Member States.

In this context, developing a comprehensive vision, policies and strategies to counter online disinformation becomes a major task for politicians and legislators. Decisions should take into account the political-social specifics and legal tradition within each individual country or community. Alongside these processes, major online platforms are also developing company policies to manage *harmful online content*, including disinformation.

The EU has been trying to be innovative and to choose an approach to disinformation that is going to best guarantee the protection of the European citizens³. The public discussions have verified the general opinion that the growing threat of misinformation, along with its negative effects, are already a symptom of the need to reformulate the rights and obligations of all stakeholders in the digital environment, so that the EU citizens could have access to quality information⁴.

1 Bechmann, A. (2020) *Tackling Disinformation and Infodemics Demands Media Policy Changes*. In: Digital Journalism, 8:6, pp. 855-863

2 EEAS Press Team (24.10.2022) *Russia/Ukraine: EEAS launches a new tool to help navigate in disinformation environment*. Available at: https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/russiaukraine-eeas-launches-new-tool-help-navigate-disinformation-environment_en?s=177

3 Yurukova, M. (2021) *The EU is in a process of searching solutions to counter disinformation online – possible approaches*. In: A collection of reports from the international conference entitled “Disinformation: the new challenges”, Sofia, the “St. Kliment Ohridski” University Publishers, pp. 151-172

4 Yurukova, M. (2021) *Opportunities for and risks to the Digital Services Act in relation to countering disinformation online*. In: The electronic scientific journal entitled “Rhetoric Online”, No 3.

The main problem – disinformation in a digital environment as an obstacle to access to quality information

Maintaining quality and reliable information is the main goal of the media system in a democratic society. Online misinformation is a challenge to ensuring quality information in a digital environment. Therefore, countering it should be part of the tools of the media system. In this context, the European public sphere faces diverse challenges related to countering disinformation. Some of them are common to all countries in the world and related to the very nature of disinformation in the digital environment, but others are specifically European and stem from the EU's chosen countermeasures.

From the very beginning of historical knowledge of the world and man, one can find examples of disinformation. From the perspective of history, philosophy and the social sciences, the creation and dissemination of false information has been an element of human nature and of social relations. From a legal point of view, disinformation is also not a new phenomenon. In Great Britain, for example, the term *false news* can be found in the first codification of English law, namely in the Statute of Westminster of 1275. The dissemination of false news was considered to be a political crime and those who told false stories provoking “dissensions between the king and his people” were imprisoned. In 1674, a Proclamation to restrain the spreading of false news was issued on behalf of the king in London.⁵ While in France, as early as 1810, the penal code punished speculators who, by means of “false and slanderous rumors, spread deliberately among the public” had caused the prices of commodities to rise or to fall. The expression *false news* (*nouvelles fausses*) was used in a law of 27 July, 1849, which used to punish “the dishonest publications or the reproduction of false news likely to disturb the public tranquility and peace”. This provision was further extended and included in Article 27 of the Freedom of the Press Act of July, 1881, which stipulated a punishment in case someone's honor or reputation had been defamed, that is, it regulated both the protection of libel and of reputation⁶. A great number of other pieces of legislation have already got provisions dealing with the dissemination of false information. In the US, there has been such a practice in the course of the past 100 years, when fake news were declared to be unprotected speech, if they affected the public interest.

The above examples indicate that fake news are not a novelty, but the media ecosystem⁷ is changing as a result of new technologies. In the 21st century, however, the old phenomenon has been spreading in a new environment, in new ways, and through different channels, quite unlike the familiar ones. The *network society*⁸ functions according to new rules and mechanisms. Today, in a digital environment, everyone can not only get information online, but can also choose their sources from a huge number

5 Van Heekeren, M. (2020) The spreading fire of fake news, Available from: <https://www.sl.nsw.gov.au/stories/spreading-fire-fake-news>

6 Flandrin, A. (2018) *Avant les «fake news», les fausses nouvelles*, In: Le Monde, Available from: https://www.lemonde.fr/idees/article/2018/02/04/avant-les-fake-news-les-fausses-nouvelles_5251562_3232.html

7 The term “media ecosystem” was first coined in 2001 by the renowned scientist Henry Jenkins. See in: Wiard, V. (2019) *News Ecology and News Ecosystems*. This term can be later found in Henry Jenkin's works in the context of the transmedia narrative and the convergent culture theories, in which he discusses the clash between the old and the new media.

8 Castells, M. (1996) *The rise of the network society: The information age: Economy, society, and culture* (Vol. 1). Oxford: John Wiley & Sons.

of media content creators – some of them professional journalists, while the others include anonymous authors, bots or the opinions of non-vetted people.

This environment creates new challenges. The process of large-scale change in the field of public communication and publicity is characterized by a decrease in the importance of traditional media, experts and authorities on the news flow. The sense of the rise of disinformation comes to the fore. Social media platforms are usurping the role of traditional media. Television, radio and the press have the duty to uphold democratic principles and to be a mediator between the government and the public in compliance with journalistic standards and norms. Companies working in the field of information and communication technologies do not have these duties and responsibilities, regardless of the fact that they take over some of the functions of journalists and the media. Moreover, in line with the digital transformation and the new way of public communication, traditional media are becoming dependent on social networks. In order to reach their audience, traditional media become both users of online platforms and creators of content in them. We are witnessing a process of *platformization* where social media acts as an intermediary between its users and traditional news media. But while the credibility of traditional sources of factual information continues to be questioned, platforms are not responsible for the content they offer their users.

The law has been slow to reflect these changes in a timely manner for a number of complex reasons. First, technology is evolving faster than law can respond to the effects that innovation produces. Second, there is no single answer to the question of whether harmful but legal content should continue to escape regulation simply because it is not illegal. Third, complex mechanisms make it difficult to determine who should be responsible in different situations. Fourth, the process of finding a balance between countering disinformation and restricting freedom of expression continues.

All this alters the familiar media ecosystem to the extent that states do not have functioning tools to effectively protect freedom of speech so as to ensure the creation, delivery and receipt of quality information in a digital environment. The inadequacy of the media system in relation to digital realities leads to an increase in the negative effects of disinformation, which, combined with the lack of trust in a time of post-truth and information overload, negatively affects the ability of individuals and communities to defend their interests based on facts. The result is that citizens doubt the accumulated public knowledge and official sources, and their emotions become decisive for their elections. Disinformation, the lack of quality content and the decreasing importance of such information for society, the violation of communication rights, the misuse of personal data, the low trust in institutions, in official data and in traditional media and the rise of conspiracy theories are clear signs of the need for a new media and news ecosystem in the digital age.

In this sense, the main challenge to the implementation of the European approach to combating disinformation is related to its integration into the overall reform of the digital space in the EU. The complexity of the interrelationships between all the major actors (both traditional and new) require their adaptation to the new media ecosystem to be tailored to the ways in which the Internet, algorithms and digital services operate. Successful countering of disinformation is related to the creation of an effective media

ecosystem in the digital age, which has the necessary protective mechanisms to meet the challenges of reaching quality information to people in the information society.

Introduction to the European approach to countering disinformation

The European approach tries to give a balanced response to the discussed challenges in countering disinformation. Disinformation became the subject of EU policies in 2015, at which time the Union recognized as a major problem disinformation campaigns and propaganda coming from third countries⁹. In 2018, the EU adopted a *comprehensive disinformation counteracting approach*¹⁰, which went beyond the actions in the security domain. In a *Communication* dated 26 April 2018, and entitled “Tackling disinformation online: a European approach”¹¹, the European Commission defines the scope and adopts its own definition of disinformation¹². The clear definition of the term makes it possible for it to be countered by the EU.

The main applied-practical result of the same Communication is the introduction of a self-regulation tool in the field – the Code of Practice in relation to online disinformation.¹³ It is signed by major online platforms, advertisers and advertising industry including Facebook, Twitter, Google, etc. The assessment of the work of the Code within the first year of its existence is that there has been considerable, but not sufficient, success. This assessment led to the Commission’s follow-up, which included a *Communication on the Action Plan for European Democracy*¹⁴, some proposals for a *Digital Services Act (DSA)*,¹⁵ a *Digital Markets Act (DMA)*¹⁶, and the *Communication with Guidelines for Strengthening the Code of Conduct*. The European Commission’s *Communication* in relation to disinformation of February 2022, entitled “*Shaping Europe’s Digital Future*” placed an emphasis on the achievement of an “*open, democratic and sustainable society*”.¹⁷ This particular Communication focused upon the encouragement of media pluralism, on the quality content and the digital skills, as well as on the use of the digital technologies and solutions.

The European Democracy Action Plan is a non-legislative instrument of a program nature¹⁸, which laid the beginnings of a new change in the approach to disinformation counteraction in the EU. The entire 2020 package of measures was making an attempt

9 As a result of the Summit convened on 19-20 March, 2015, an East StratCom Task Force was established at the European External Action Service (EEAS). The EEAS StratCom Task Force has been subsequently responsible also for the work of the Rapid Alert System (RAS) established in 2019.

10 European Commission (EC). COM(2018) 236 final. *Tackling disinformation online: a European Approach*.

11 Ibid.

12 According to the EU, “Disinformation is understood as verifiably false or misleading information that is created, presented and disseminated for economic gain or to intentionally deceive the public, and may cause public harm.” A clear explanation has been made of what is not meant by disinformation, namely “reporting errors, satire and parody, or clearly identified partisan news and commentary.” See: European Commission (EC). COM(2018) 236 final. *Tackling disinformation online: a European Approach*

13 Code of Practice on Disinformation

14 European Commission. (EC). COM(2020) 790 final. *On the European democracy action plan*.

15 European Commission (EC). COM(2020) 825 final. Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on a Single Market for Digital Services (the Digital Services Act) and amending Directive 2000/31/EC.

16 European Commission (EC). COM(2020) 842 final. Proposal for a regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on contestable and fair markets in the digital sector (the Digital Markets Act).

17 European Commission. (EC). COM(2020) 67 final. *Shaping Europe’s digital future*.

18 Ogyanovna, N. (2021) „*There will be no Ministry of Truth in the EU: on the trail of a promise (the EU policy on disinformation)*.” In: A collection of reports from the international conference entitled “Disinformation: the new challenges”, Sofia, the “St. Kliment Ohridski” University Publishers, pp. 92-118

to offer a more comprehensive approach to disinformation than the one introduced in 2018.

In conclusion, for the relatively short period between 2015 and 2022, the approach to disinformation within the EU is moving from sectoral (in the security sphere) to horizontal (affecting the overall functioning of the digital single market). Initially, the Union chooses to apply soft law instruments, and subsequently adds a regulatory instrument. After all, the EU is undertaking a horizontal policy to counter disinformation. It was built up as a *double safety net* model, that is, a model of co-regulation. It has two main pillars. The two pillars are intended to be interconnected and complementary. The innovative framework aims for “transparency to regulators and users and accountability of platforms without interaction devolving into content censorship”¹⁹ The first pillar is *the Code of Practice (self-regulation)*, developed further in 2022. The second one is *Legislative Package on the Digital Services (regulation)*. Its provisions go far beyond the scope of disinformation, but it is considered the main piece of legislation relevant to countering it. Although the regulation was approved in 2022, it has not yet entered into force. This co-regulatory approach has been supported by additional disinformation countering mechanisms on an EU and a Member State level, including: investment in education; media and digital literacy initiatives; a *Rapid Alert System (RAS)*; the *European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO)*, etc.

Countering disinformation in the EU is seen as part of a major reform in the governance of the digital space. Actions taken in the area are in sync with the overall Digital Single Market Strategy. The aim is to ensure a balanced approach to the protection of the rights of both citizens and all participants in the digital environment, which will lead to competitive advantages for the European market.

The double safety net and the underlying components in the European policy implementation tools take into account the way the internet works, the main channels of disinformation and the need for comprehensive measures involving all stakeholders. The European framework and the countermeasures provided in have been met with approval among international experts and academic circles. However, the implementation of the European approach to combating disinformation entails many specific challenges and risks of different nature and degree of significance. Bringing together and synchronizing twenty-seven national policies is a complex task. Even more so in a context where some countries have specific legislation and each has its own specific context and traditions in the field.

Differences in the implementation between the Member States

The different implementation of the European approach to countering disinformation by the Member States stands out as one of the key challenges facing the EU. Differences in implementation between countries have been reported in numerous analytical and expert analyses, including a 2021 report by the European Court of Auditors entitled *„Disinformation affecting the EU: tackled but not tamed”*²⁰. It pointed to the lack of an adequate framework for monitoring the implementation of both the Action Plan against Disinformation and the European Democracy Action Plan. Emphasis is placed on the

¹⁹ Ibid.

²⁰ European Court of Auditors. (2021) Special Report 09/2021: *Disinformation affecting the EU: tackled but not tamed*.

lack of feedback on their implementation by Member States. The methods of monitoring, analysis and evaluation of the commitment of the EU countries in the process of implementing the tools to fight against disinformation have been criticized.

The significant differences between Member States call into question the effectiveness of the chosen approach as a whole. The reasons for these discrepancies are complex. This is due both to the legal traditions in the field, as well as to the specifics of the digital policy and the political will of the authorities in the respective countries. For example, there are Member States that implement legislative measures to counter online disinformation, such as Germany and France, and others that rely on self-regulation by platforms. The engagement of Member States in the process of forming strategies and policies to counter disinformation online diverges significantly. The varying degree of commitment, as well as political will, also affects the participation of countries in the implementation of the approach, which, in turn, leads to varying degrees of effectiveness.

The Rapid Alert System, for example, has been assessed as a useful information sharing tool, which has not been developing its full potential²¹. One of the goals of the institutional instrument is to build common situational awareness and coordination among Member States. Achieving this goal is hindered because engagement within the system has been demonstrated by a limited number of Member States – about one third. Meetings of the National Contact Points are held quarterly, but the participation of different countries varies considerably.²² The result is that the System does not lead to a significant development of the policy for countering disinformation at the level of Member States and, in this sense, does not fully fulfill its set goals.

Another example of the stark differences is the uneven participation of Member States in the European Media Literacy Week. In March 2019, over 320 events were organized under the initiative, reaching 360 by the end of September 2020, with almost half of all events taking place in France, followed by Belgium, while there are a small number of Member States that have not at all hosted events, among which are Bulgaria, the Czech Republic and Slovakia.²³

The European Digital Media Observatory (EDMO) has also spotted varying degrees of representation between countries. There are eight EDMO hubs, some of them operating within a couple of countries. About half of the EU countries are not covered by the EDMO observations. New hubs are expected to be established with the view of extending the scope and the geographical coverage of the EDMO network across the EU, which would at least formally help reduce some of the disparities between the EU countries.

In the latest European Commission proposals, an attempt is made to strengthen the role of states and strengthen their commitment in the implementation of the various tools to counter disinformation, which is expected to minimize inequalities between states.

Implementation differences between the platforms

The ability of platforms to self-regulate across EU countries in a similar way becomes another key challenge to the effectiveness of the approach applied. Analyses carried

21 Ibid.

22 Ibid.

23 Ibid.

so far²⁴ report a lack of similarity in the implementation of the Code of Practice on disinformation by its signatories. Some of them provide more detailed information, while others fulfill their obligations rather more formally. Their commitment varies from country to country.

An additional challenge is the lack of data for each Member State. Usually, the information presented is general for the EU. There is a lack of clarity regarding the implementation of commitments by platforms at national level. The 2021 study of the *Avaaz* global movement related to the spread of misinformation on the COVID-19 topic²⁵, reveals some rather important trends. It indicates not only that Facebook has been serving the American market much better than the European one, but also that there have been significant differences between the individual EU countries. One of the main trends has identified that the English-language content has been a couple of times faster and better treated than the information published in any other EU language. *Facebook* has been almost a week slower in flagging the fake non-English content. Flagging of fake content in English takes usually 24 days, while if the content is in another European language – it takes 30 days.²⁶ Research in the field has revealed that the online platforms do not treat the different countries in the same manner, rather on the contrary: depending on the degree of importance of the national markets for their businesses, they treat them differently, by developing projects and tools designed for certain markets or in certain languages alone, which further creates a differentiated application of the European model depending on the individual countries.

Differences in the application of European instruments by online platforms pose additional challenges to the fight against disinformation in Member States and across the EU. The platforms are expected to make commitments outside *the Code*, as well. According to the *EU Action Plan against Disinformation*, the online platforms and the *Rapid Alert System* contact points should cooperate; however, there is no information that this has been the case thus far.

Risks of over-application or non-application

The aim of the upcoming legislative changes in the EU, including the *DSA*, is to transform the European digital future so that the EU could become competitive on the world stage and build up a European media system suitable for the online environment and the modern realities. The chosen European approach is highly appreciated by experts. But whether the double safety net provides enough protection for citizens remains the focus of debate.

There are serious concerns about the effectiveness and extent of implementation of the *Digital Services Act*. Implementation is extremely dependent on national legislators and regulators.²⁷ In addition to the risk of limited application of the regulation in the EU countries, one should not forget the danger of over-application (removal of

24 Ibid.

25 AVAAZ. (20 April 2021) *Left Behind: How Facebook is neglecting Europe's infodemic*. Available from: https://secure.avaaz.org/campaign/en/facebook_neglect_europe_infodemic/

26 Ibid.

27 Ogyananova, N. (2021) „*There will be no Ministry of Truth in the EU: on the trail of a promise (the EU policy on disinformation)*.” In: A collection of reports from the international conference entitled “Disinformation: the new challenges”, Sofia, the “St. Kliment Ohridski” University Publishers, pp. 92-118

content for the purpose of reinsurance against sanctions), which can affect the right to free expression of both users and platforms.²⁸

The proposed *Digital Services Act Package* has significant merits and advantages, but it regulates an extremely complex, dynamic and hitherto poorly managed environment, which implies numerous challenges of a different nature.

The *Digital Services Act* provides for measures following a risk-based approach. The regulation is comprehensive, differentiated and adequate to modern realities. Its action can be seen as an instrument of both preventive and follow-up policy. It applies to both illegal and legal but harmful content, such as disinformation.²⁹

The *DSA* has made significant progress in relation to the issues that are already commonly understood, such as ensuring more transparency of advertising and the algorithms, the systemic risk management, the differentiation between the different types of digital service providers, and the greater engagement of EU countries. The obligations of the platforms set out in the *DSA* are intended to make these platforms much more accountable to the fundamental rights³⁰. It provides for differentiation of service providers and different obligations according to the category in which they fall. New obligations have been introduced for online intermediaries, most notably those for large online platforms (VLOPs) and large online search engines (VLOSEs). Large platforms or search engines are those that reach more than 10% of the 450 million European monthly users.

Despite all this, a need remains for further debate on how to reconcile the regulation of harmful but legal content with the protection of the right to free expression.³¹ The legislative package provides rules for the removal of online illegal goods, services or content. This approach carries huge risks, because it can also lead to excessive empowerment of platforms, placing the responsibility on them to decide, and in a non-transparent way at the moment, what content is legal and what is not. The big danger in this approach is that the EU would allow platforms to be the ones to censor misinformation according to their criteria.³²

The *Digital Services Act* provides insufficiently clear wording that online platforms must act in good faith and in a diligent manner, without explaining what the standard for such good faith action is. The lack of legal certainty is compounded by the unclear scope of such privileged voluntary measures. In this sense, one of the main risks related to the content removal strategies has to do with the danger of overblocking. Since the host providers take advantage only of the limited liability for third-party content, when they expeditiously remove content, which they “know” to be illegal, the platforms themselves would likely block content in order to avoid the threat of liability.³³ This

²⁸ Ibid.

²⁹ Ibid.

³⁰ Tambini, D. (2021) *Media policy in 2021: As the EU takes on the tech giants, will the UK?* Available from: <https://blogs.lse.ac.uk/mediase/2021/01/12/media-policy-in-2021-as-the-eu-takes-on-the-tech-giants-will-the-uk/>

³¹ Yurukova, M. (2021) *Opportunities for and risks to the Digital Services Act in relation to countering disinformation online*. In: The electronic scientific journal entitled “Rhetoric Online”, No 3.

³² Ognyanova, K. (2021) *Network approaches to misinformation evaluation and correction*. In: Networks, Knowledge Brokers, and the Public Policymaking Process, 1–23

³³ Directive 2000/31/EO of the European Parliament and of the Council of June 8, 2000, on certain legal aspects of the information society services, in particular, electronic commerce in the Internal Market (the Electronic Commerce Directive)

would lead to imbalances and undue restriction of freedom of speech in a certain case. Balancing between countering disinformation and protecting freedom of speech in this sense becomes a major challenge for the implementation of the European regulatory instrument.

Conclusion

Disinformation and the effects of its spread in a digital environment pose a challenge to the media system. Their rise is an obstacle to access to quality information. They are a symptom of the need to create a new information system adequate for the 21st century. In this context, the EU has started a process of reforming the governance of the digital space. Tools to counter disinformation are part of this reform. The main objective is to protect and guarantee freedom of expression in the digital environment by introducing such restrictions that serve to achieve this objective and do not lead to a disproportionate restriction of rights.

The European approach to countering online disinformation presents an adequate and innovative framework, but its implementation faces challenges of a different nature.

First, the differences in the implementation of the European approach in the EU Member States represent an obstacle to its effectiveness. In about a third of them, active behavior is observed in terms of both the development of the European policy in the field and the use of the instruments provided at the supranational level, but in the remaining countries the results achieved are limited and an insufficient degree of commitment is observed.

Second, in addition to differences in implementation by Member States, there are also differences by platforms. Major platforms show varying degrees of commitment to the Code of Practice obligations across countries.

The third challenge is related to the risk of over-application of the Digital Services Act and the tools envisaged in the European approach, which may lead to violations in the protection of the rights of both users and platforms. At the other extreme, there is the possibility of reaching the non-application of European instruments in the Member States. Although the Digital Services Act is a regulation and should be directly implemented, there are many issues related to its implementation that need to be resolved at national level. The lack of political will, clearly defined responsibilities and coordination regarding the implementation of the European framework for countering disinformation can minimize and practically nullify the effect of the instruments provided at the supranational level.

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